

Supplementary Table S1. Effects of duration on a high-concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogetic feed additive on the profile of volatile fatty acids in the free fluid of the reticulum of non-lactating cows (values are daily means).

Item	Duration on high-concentrate and feed supplementation ¹										SE ³	P-values ⁴		
	Wk 0		Wk 1		Wk 2		Wk 3		Wk 4			DU	SU	I
	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY				
Total VFA, mM	86.2	84.7	111	106	109	105	112 ^x	103 ^y	117	112	4.06	<0.01	0.12	0.78
% of total VFA														
Acetate	65.7	66.7	59.2	58.3	59.1 ^a	55.4 ^b	60.1	60.2	60.4	61.2	1.54	<0.01	0.58	0.01
Propionate	18.1	17.8	19.7	20.1	21.8	24.0	21.4	21.8	21.7	23.3	1.46	<0.01	0.85	0.28
Butyrate ²	10.7	10.8	15.9 ^y	16.6 ^x	13.9 ^b	15.1 ^a	13.6	13.5	12.9 ^a	11.4 ^b	0.45	<0.01	0.91	<0.01
Valerate	1.67	1.68	2.11	2.27	2.08	2.43	1.81	1.62	1.92	1.80	0.11	<0.01	0.97	<0.01
Isobutyrate ²	1.28	1.26	0.82	0.81	0.89	0.87	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.91	0.06	<0.01	0.95	0.82
Isovalerate	2.09	2.14	1.59	1.65	1.54	1.76	1.40	1.47	1.44	1.51	0.12	<0.01	0.67	0.65
Acetate:Propionate	3.71	3.76	3.14	2.96	2.93	2.67	3.20	3.35	2.97	2.82	0.27	<0.01	0.80	0.32

¹CON: A control diet without phytogetic supplementation; PHY: supplementation with 0.04% of a phytogetic feed additive consisting of a combination of menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

²Because of a lack of normal distribution, data were subjected to log transformation prior to statistical analysis, and then back-transformed.

³The largest standard error of the mean. Means include the values of samples collected 0, 4, 8 and 12 h post-feeding.

⁴P-values for the main effects of duration on high concentrate in weeks (DU), the main effects of feed supplementation (SU), and the interaction of duration on high concentrate × feed supplementation (I).

^{a,b}Within corresponding week, means with different superscripts differed between CON and PHY ($P < 0.05$).

^{x,y}Within corresponding week, means with different superscript tended to differ between CON and PHY ($0.05 < P \leq 0.10$).

Supplementary Table S2. Effects of duration on a high-concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogetic feed additive on the profile of volatile fatty acids in feces of non-lactating cows (values are daily means).

Item	Duration on high-concentrate and feed supplementation ¹										SE ³	<i>P</i> -values ⁴		
	Wk 0		Wk 1		Wk 2		Wk 3		Wk 4			DU	SU	I
	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY	CON	PHY				
Total VFA, mM	50.3	50.6	85.1	89.2	77.2	77.1	76.0	72.7	74.1	74.5	3.56	<0.01	0.74	0.85
% of total VFA														
Acetate	76.8	76.6	75.4	76.3	73.7	73.7	74.0	73.5	74.4	75.2	0.50	<0.01	0.72	0.18
Propionate	14.6	14.6	15.9	15.5	15.9	15.8	15.5 ^b	16.7 ^a	15.7	15.9	0.28	<0.01	0.56	<0.05
Butyrate ²	4.70	4.80	5.86	5.91	6.57	6.43	6.80 ^a	5.51 ^b	6.40 ^a	5.93 ^b	0.20	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01
Valerate	1.22	1.33	1.05	0.97	1.34	1.36	1.20 ^b	1.36 ^a	1.21	1.12	0.05	<0.01	0.33	<0.01
Isobutyrate ²	1.50	1.48	0.97	0.76	1.38	1.27	1.26 ^b	1.57 ^a	1.22	1.06	0.14	<0.01	0.27	<0.01
Isovalerate ²	0.97	1.05	0.60	0.42	0.95	0.99	0.88	1.13	0.81 ^x	0.64 ^y	0.16	<0.01	0.61	<0.01
Acetate:Propionate	5.33	5.28	4.77	4.94	4.69	4.76	4.80	4.47	4.77	4.78	0.12	<0.01	0.72	0.09

¹CON: A control diet without phytogetic supplementation; PHY: supplementation with 0.04% of a phytogetic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high-concentrate feeding.

²Because of a lack of normal distribution, data were subjected to log transformation prior to statistical analysis, and then back-transformed.

³The largest standard error of the mean. Means include the values of samples collected 0, 4, 8 and 12 h post-feeding.

⁴*P*-values for the main effects of duration on high concentrate in weeks (DU), the main effects of feed supplementation (SU), and the interaction of duration on high-concentrate × feed supplementation (I).

^{a,b}Within corresponding week, means with different superscripts differed between CON and PHY ($P < 0.05$).

^{x,y}Within corresponding week, means with different superscript tended to differ between CON and PHY ($0.05 < P \leq 0.10$).

Supplementary Figure S1. Diurnal variation of ruminal pH in non-lactating Holstein cows consuming forage or a high concentrate ration without supplementation (CON) or supplemented (PHY) with a phytogenic feed additive. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

Supplementary Figure S2. Effects of duration on a high concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive on fecal pH post-feeding in non-lactating cows. CON: Control without supplementation, PHY: Supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

Supplementary Figure S3. Total VFA (A), acetate (B), propionate (C) and butyrate (D) in the reticulum, free fluid (FF) of rumen, particle-associated fluid (PAF) of rumen and rectum for non-lactating cows according to duration on a high concentrate diet not supplemented (CON) or supplemented with a phytogenic feed additive (PHY). *P*-values for time post-feeding (reticulum, rumen-FF, and rectum): Total VFA (<0.01, <0.01, 0.22), acetate (<0.01, <0.01, 0.42), propionate (<0.01, <0.01, 0.29), butyrate (<0.01, <0.01, <0.01).

Supplementary Figure S4. Valerate (A), isobutyrate (B) and isovalerate (C) in the reticulum, free fluid (FF) of rumen, particle-associated fluid (PAF) of rumen and rectum for non-lactating cows according to duration on a high concentrate diet not supplemented (CON) or supplemented with a phytogenic additive (PHY). *P*-values for time post-feeding (reticulum, rumen-FF, and rectum): valerate (<0.01, <0.01, 0.46), isobutyrate (<0.01, <0.01, <0.01), isovalerate (0.12, 0.16, 0.50). Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

Duration $P < 0.01$; PHY $P = 0.37$; Location $P < 0.01$; Duration \times PHY \times Location $P < 0.01$

Supplementary Figure S5. Effects of duration on a high concentrate diet and supplementation with a phylogenetic feed additive on D-lactate concentration in particle-associated fluid and free fluid of the rumen of non-lactating cows. CON: Control without supplementation, PHY: Supplementation with a phylogenetic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

Duration $P < 0.01$; PHY $P = 0.06$; Location $P < 0.01$; Duration \times PHY \times Location $P = 0.87$

Supplementary Figure S6. Effects of duration on a high concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive on L-lactate concentration in particle-associated fluid and free fluid of the rumen of non-lactating cows. CON: Control without supplementation, PHY: Supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high concentrate feeding.

Duration $P < 0.01$; PHY $P = 0.19$; Location $P < 0.01$; Duration \times PHY \times Location $P = 0.08$

Supplementary Figure S7. Effects of duration on a high-concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive on total lactate concentration in particle-associated fluid and free fluid of the rumen of non-lactating cows. CON: Control without supplementation, PHY: Supplementation with a phytogenic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high-concentrate feeding.

Supplementary Figure S8. Effects of duration on a high-concentrate diet and supplementation with a phytogetic feed additive on concentration of ammonia in the free fluid of the rumen of non-lactating cows. CON: Control without supplementation, PHY: Supplementation with a phytogetic feed additive based on menthol, thymol and eugenol. Wk 0 corresponds to measurements taken before the start of high-concentrate feeding.